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The impact of *Survive – Support for Survivors of Rape and Sexual Abuse*:
An Independent Evaluation

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Foreword by Mags Godderidge

CEO of Survive (Support for survivors of rape and sexual abuse)

Survive is so grateful to Dr Nathalie Noret and Dr Susan Hillyard for expanding the knowledge base on sexual trauma and its prevalence and impact. This independent evaluation of our stabilisation counselling service supports what we have always believed but not necessarily been able to evidence: that

- sexual trauma has a long-term and sometimes lifelong impact on our clients' physical, mental, and emotional health;
- *Survive* reduces reliance on over-stretched NHS mental health services locally; and
- *Survive* counselling really does transform the lives of adult survivors, helping them move forward after sexual trauma

Survive could not do what it does without the skills, dedication and commitment of its team of less than 15 FTE staff- without whom the work detailed in this report would not be possible. The teams' resolve and resilience should be acknowledged and applauded, and the compassion and kindness they show to survivors commended as they give them hope for a future better than the past.

Survive remains the only specialist sexual violence agency in York and North Yorkshire that has achieved conformance with The Survivors Trust UKAS Accredited National Service Standards. The Survivor Trust accreditation of specialist support services like *Survive* aligns with the newly introduced UKAS inspection of Sexual Assault Referral Centres (SARCs) to create an externally verified and unified approach to quality assurance inspection across sexual violence services locally. Whilst our accreditation assures survivors, commissioners and funders that our services, staff, management structures, practice and governance have evidenced international best practice in the delivery of specialist sexual violence support services, this independent evaluation assures them that what we deliver actually works.

Survive's vision continues to be for a world without sexual violence and abuse. Until then, we will continue to provide safe spaces and kind, caring and compassionate services that really do help adult survivors heal, rebuild and thrive.

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SECTION 1

Background

In this section of the report, we highlight the nature, prevalence and impact of child sexual abuse, rape and sexual assault.

Child Sexual Abuse

The Crown Prosecution Service¹ define child sexual abuse (CSA) as encompassing a range of criminal offences, including physical contact (e.g., touching) and non-physical offences (e.g., sharing sexual images of children). Such behaviours happen when a child or young person (defined as a person under the age of 18) is forced, coerced or enticed into taking part in sexual activity.

The Prevalence of Child Sexual Abuse

There are no exact figures in the UK detailing the number of children/adults who are experiencing or have experienced sexual abuse. However, there are many indicators of the prevalence of CSA in the UK:

- The NSPCC² estimates that 1 in 20 children has been sexually abused.
- The Centre of Expertise on Child Sexual Abuse³ suggests that 1 in 10 children has experienced some form of sexual abuse before they are 16.
- Analysis of police-recorded child sexual abuse and exploitation (CSE) reported that there were 115,489 CSAE offences in 2023⁴.
- Sexual Assault Referral Centres in England had contact with 9,533 children in 2023/2024, half of those under 18 were aged 13 or under at their first consultation, with 1 in 6 aged 0-5⁵.
- In 2025, the Home Office suggested that 7.5% of all adults in England and Wales are estimated to have been a victim of sexual abuse before the age of 16⁶.
- There are approximately 400,000 searches for online child sexual abuse material in the UK every month⁶.

Rape and Sexual Assault

The law defines rape as when someone puts their penis into someone's vagina, bottom, or mouth without their consent⁷. Sexual Assault is defined as any sexual touching of any body part or object without someone's consent, this can include kissing⁷.

The prevalence of Rape and Sexual Assault

Like CSA, it can be difficult to determine exact rates of rape and sexual assault due to the underreporting of these experiences. However, national data give some indication of the prevalence of these behaviours:

- In the year ending March 2022, the police recorded 193,566 sexual offences, the highest level recorded⁸.
- In the year ending March 2025, approximately 34% of all sexual offences recorded by the police were for rape⁹.
- In March 2025, the Office for National Statistics reported that in the previous year, approximately 900,000 adults (people aged 16 and over) had experienced a sexual assault in England and Wales⁹.
- Rape Crisis England and Wales states that 1 in 4 women and 1 in 18 men have been raped or sexually assaulted since the age of 16 and that, as of March 2025, the total number of women in England and Wales who have experienced rape or sexual assault since the age of 16 is 6.3 million¹⁰.
- 51.8% of victims report being repeatedly victimised, i.e. experiencing sexual violence more than once, and 23.6% report experiencing such violence more than 3 times¹¹.

The Impact

The impact of CSA, rape and sexual assault on a survivor is often immense. Specifically attributing problems to CSA, rape, and sexual assault is difficult, as every individual is a different person with diverse backgrounds and circumstances. Each will respond to the harm in their own way, and the impacts may evolve, especially for the child survivor. Intersectional factors, i.e., culture, ethnicity, social backgrounds, gender, sexual orientation, (dis)ability, will mean the impact is unique from individual to individual.

CSA, rape and sexual assault can lead to a range of negative outcomes, including:

- Poor mental health and emotional problems, such as anxiety, depression, dissociation, PTSD, suicidal thoughts, eating disorders, self-harm, substance abuse, insomnia and other sleep-related issues, low self-esteem and confidence. A survivor may experience a number of these issues, all of which will also have an impact on their mental health¹².
- Physical health impacts such as injury due to penetration, sexually transmitted diseases, pregnancy/abortion¹³.
- Other possible physical complications are considerable, ranging from gastrointestinal issues such as IBS, problems with pregnancies, chronic illnesses such as arthritis and other inflammatory disorders¹⁴.
- Physical health problems associated with the mental health issues, i.e., many self-harm actions, will result in physical injuries¹⁵.

The Impact

CSA, rape and sexual assault can also lead to a range of relationship and social challenges, including:

- Sexual difficulties affecting the survivor's response to sexual desire, arousal, including both hypersexuality and hyposexuality¹⁵.
- Difficulty managing and maintaining relationships, which include problems with trust and the ability to develop strong and healthy attachments. Sometimes doubting their ability to be a good friend/partner/parent¹⁵.
- Educational and employment impacts, disengagement from educational studies and difficulty in sustaining employment, all of which are frequently due to mental health problems resulting from the experience of historical/non-recent and ongoing sexual abuse trauma¹⁵.

All these issues have a wider impact on families, friends, colleagues, and society, both emotionally and financially. The costs of the unrecognised and untreated complex trauma of CSA, rape and sexual assault are profound. Such impacts include reduced quality of life, decreased life expectancy, and lost productivity, as well as increased involvement with public-funded organisations such as healthcare, social care, and criminal justice services¹⁶. Such impacts also entail costs for the state.

New research suggests that the lifetime cost of sexual violence and abuse in England and Wales is £400 billion.

Rape Crisis 2025

The cost of providing counselling to **one** client at *Survive*.

Specifically in York & North Yorkshire

Domain	Lifetime cost in York	Lifetime cost in Yorkshire & Humber
Health & Social Care (Physical & Mental Health, & Social care)	£79,052,642.20	£2,045,380,096.20
Cost to the Justice System (Police, Criminal Justice, Civil Justice, Incarceration)	£174,238,540.00	£4,508,186,340.00
Total cost Includes the above and cost to education, specialist services, QALY loss and productivity loss)	£1,036,865,785.06	£26,827,498,489.26

Note: Costs based on the Vision Sexual Violence cost estimate tool¹⁷.

**“Talking about sexual assault isn’t easy,
but no one should suffer in silence.”**

Minister of State for Courts and Legal Services, Sarah Sackman¹⁸

Help-Seeking & Reporting

As a traumatic experience, encouraging survivors to access help for their experiences is crucial to providing appropriate mental health support. Professional support for those who have experienced CSA varies but can include medical, practical, or emotional support provided by healthcare, social care, and criminal justice organisations, as well as specialist voluntary/charitable bodies. However, the level and nature of support available can be inconsistent¹⁹. The Independent Inquiry into Child Sexual Abuse (IICSA) raised concerns about the availability and suitability of current therapeutic support offered to survivors of child sexual abuse in England and Wales, recommending a national guarantee of specialist therapeutic support¹⁹. Survivors told the IICSA of their frustrations with non-specialist generic support services, highlighting the need for specialist, trauma-based counsellors¹⁹.

Seeking support following experiences of CSA, rape, and sexual assault can be challenging, while a range of interventions and campaigns focus on encouraging survivors to seek help, many do not. Barriers to help-seeking include feelings of shame, blame and guilt, minimising experiences, alongside socio-cultural barriers such as fear of being judged or not being believed. Therefore, many survivors require support but are fearful about reporting and seeking support for their experiences²⁰. Yet with the appropriate support, survivors can and do recover. Trauma-informed counselling is one method of providing support, and evidence suggests it can have a profound impact on survivors.

Trauma-Informed Support

A trauma-informed approach is grounded in an understanding of the survivor's life experiences and circumstances, especially their trauma history. In comparison to other forms of therapeutic intervention, the trauma-informed approach shifts the focus from discussions around *what is wrong with you?* to focus on *what happened to you?* This approach is used to design and inform support, thereby avoiding further trauma, paying particular attention to the survivor's need for safety, trust, collaboration, choice and empowerment^{21,22}.

For many specialist sexual violence support providers (e.g., Rape Crisis, *Survive*, Women's Aid), the delivery of trauma-informed counselling is key to improving long-term outcomes for survivors. Trauma-informed counselling plays a critical part in healing, helping survivors to:

- Understand and cope with strong and upsetting feelings
- Cope with mental health issues, i.e., nightmares or intrusive thoughts
- Reduce feelings of shame, self-blame and low self-esteem.
- Lead a 'normal' fulfilled life²³.

A trauma-informed service is an important step in ensuring survivors lead full, happy and socially productive lives^{24,25}. Evidence suggests that trauma-informed approaches can significantly reduce symptoms of trauma and improve psychological functioning in survivors of rape and sexual violence²⁶.

The Challenge

Many of the organisations that provide these specialist services are in crisis, resulting in ongoing closures and service reductions²⁷. Specialist sexual violence support services have growing client bases of individuals with multiple needs and issues, sometimes from diverse and hard-to-reach communities. All require bespoke client-focused trauma-informed support.

Despite many years of tireless campaigning, these specialist support organisations continue to struggle to remain solvent in a chaotic, ever-changing and shrinking funding landscape^{27,28}. The funding issues, problems with staff recruitment and retention, due to below-industry-norm salaries²⁸, short-term fixed contracts, limited support staff, and a reliance on volunteer goodwill²⁸, create a viability tightrope. The National Audit Office has highlighted that victim support services were under “*significant pressure*” and “*unable to meet demand*”²⁹. These specialist support organisations were specifically designed to counter the consequences of such crimes, responding to practical and political needs. They not only provide vital life-saving support for hundreds of thousands of women and children every year³⁰ but also ensure that the issue of gender based violence is a constant on any political agenda.

Yet if these organisations continue to shrink and disappear, where will the high levels of referrals from social care, GPs, mental health services²⁸ and additional self-referrals go?

SECTION 2

About *Survive*

In this section, we explain the context in York and North Yorkshire and outline the support *Survive provides*.

The Context in York and North Yorkshire

The York and North Yorkshire Combined Authority is currently the largest combined authority in England by geographical area. It covers approximately 8,300 square kilometres (roughly 3,200 square miles), making it approximately five times the size of Greater London.

- In the 2023/24 year, North Yorkshire Police recorded 668 reports of rape and 768 reports of sexual assault. Of these reports, 267 of the reports of rape and 391 of the reports of sexual assault involved a victim under the age of 18³¹.
- The financial cost of serious sexual violence crimes in York and North Yorkshire is estimated to be £2,214,101³².
- Comparisons of data from the 2022/23 with data from 2023/24 indicate a 9% rise in serious sexual offences. These data highlight the need to focus on VAWG offences³².
- Tackling VAWG is one of the key priorities for the York and North Yorkshire Combined Authority, and a key objective of the VAWG strategic plan is to enhance support services for victims³².

About *Survive*

***Survive* was established in York in 1990 as a peer-led support group for women with shared histories of child sexual abuse. Thirty-five years later, *Survive* now helps any adult survivor of sexual violence and abuse to heal, rebuild and thrive through the delivery of specialist services and trauma-specific interventions.**

***Survive* remains the only specialist sexual violence agency in York and North Yorkshire, offering free-of-charge support work, stabilisation counselling, trauma therapy and EMDR psychotherapy alongside a helpline that has achieved accreditation that aligns with UKAS's inspection of Sexual Assault Referral Centres (SARCs), providing a unified approach to quality assurance inspection across statutory and third-sector service provision.**

About *Survive*

All survivors start with a counsellor-led initial assessment to identify individual risks, needs and goals and to establish trauma history before being triaged into six sessions of support work or up to 10 sessions of stabilisation counselling. All survivors must complete stabilisation counselling before they can access up to 20 weeks of trauma therapy or EMDR psychotherapy. Those not suited to trauma therapy or Eye Movement Desensitisation and Reprocessing (EMDR) psychotherapy can access further support work or stabilisation counselling. The vast majority (77%) who access trauma therapy or EMDR psychotherapy after stabilisation counselling are adult survivors of child sexual abuse.

SECTION 3

About this project

In this section, we outline the background to and the aims of this project.

This Project

In July 2024, the College of Policing and the National Police Chiefs' Council declared that violence against women and girls (VAWG) is a “*national emergency*”³⁴. Currently, a wealth of attention is focused on preventing and reducing VAWG, and encouraging those who have been harmed to report their experiences. While encouraging reporting and support-seeking is clearly needed, this will inevitably place even greater pressure on already stretched support services.

Therefore, a better understanding of what works to support survivors of CSA, rape, and sexual assault is crucial to ensure the system adequately supports survivors and reduces the potentially negative lifetime impact of such harm. Currently, evaluations of trauma-informed approaches to support survivors of CSA, rape, and sexual assault in the UK are lacking.

Therefore, the aim of this project was to evaluate the impact of *Survive* on survivors of CSA and on survivors of rape and sexual assault.

The Aim of this Project

Specifically, through this evaluation, we aim to examine the following research questions:

- What are the victimisation experiences of clients accessing *Survive*?
- What are the health needs of clients accessing *Survive*?
- Does support from *Survive* reduce clients' need to access NHS Mental Health Services?
- Does support from *Survive* significantly reduce psychological distress and symptoms of trauma in survivors of sexual violence?
- Does support from *Survive* work effectively for male and female survivors, as well as for younger and older survivors?
- What do survivors think of the support provided by *Survive*?

SECTION 4

Method

In this section, we explain our approach to the data analysis undertaken for this project.

Method: Data

To address our research questions, we conducted a secondary data analysis of anonymised data gathered by *Survive*. As a routine part of their clinical work, *Survive* gathers data on biological sex and age, alongside measures of psychological distress and trauma. For this report, we analysed data from different pathways and referral methods -

- **Section 1:** *Survive's* general stabilisation counselling offer NHS pilot 2023/25
 - To examine the nature of victimisation experiences reported by clients accessing *Survive*, the impact of the harm on their physical health, and how support from *Survive* reduced symptoms of trauma.
- **Section 2:** *Survive's* general stabilisation counselling offer from 2023/24 to 2024/25
 - To examine how support from *Survive* reduced symptoms of psychological distress and trauma.
- **Section 3:** Qualitative client feedback data
 - To examine clients' feedback on the impact of *Survive*.

Mental Health Measures

As part of their clinical work, *Survive* complete measures of psychological distress and trauma at the start and end of the therapeutic process.

The CORE-10

The CORE-10 (Clinical Outcomes in Routine Evaluation)³⁴ is a short, well-validated measure of distress symptoms. It was designed for use in clinical settings and provides an overview of clinical symptoms, enabling practitioners to evaluate changes in symptoms before and after therapy. The CORE-10 includes symptoms capturing anxiety, depression, trauma, physical problems, functioning and risk to self. When scored, the scale provides an overall score of clinical distress, where a score of 11 or higher indicates clinically relevant distress³⁵.

The Impact of Events Scale

The Impact of Events Scale-Revised (IES-R)³⁶ is a well-validated measure of distress following a traumatic event. The scale aligns with the diagnostic criteria for Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) and captures symptoms of Intrusion, Hyper-vigilance and Avoidance. The IES-R is a useful scale for identifying clients who may require further assessment for PTSD and can be used to monitor treatment progress.

Data Analysis

To examine differences in psychological distress scores and trauma scores over time, we analysed the quantitative data collected by *Survive*. In each of the analyses presented, we report

- The mean and standard deviation of psychological distress scores, showing the mean (average) score and the variation (spread) in scores. We report this for the whole sample of clients included in the analysis, and then report this by sex and age group.
- We analysed differences in psychological distress and trauma scores using independent t-tests. These tests enable us to examine whether there is a meaningful change, indicated by a significant ($p < .001$) result.
- We also report Cohen's *d* effect size to indicate *how big a difference* is identified. Conventions in interpreting such scores suggest that $d > .2$ indicates a small difference, $d > .5$ indicates a moderate difference, and $d > .8$ indicates a large difference.
- With the psychological distress data, we also present the categories of clinically relevant psychological distress. Here, we present the number and percentage of participants in each group.
- Finally, we also analysed qualitative data using qualitative content analysis to highlight key themes in client feedback.

SECTION 5

Results: Evaluation of the NHS Pilot data

In the first results section, we report on the findings of our data analysis of *Survive's* NHS pilot project.

The NHS Pilot Project

This section of the report examines data collected during the NHS pilot project conducted from 2023/24 to 2024/25, funded by the Community Mental Health Transformation fund. A total of 57 clients accessed support from *Survive* as part of this project. To assess changes in trauma in this group of clients, we matched anonymised IES-R data for 42 clients (72.4% of all clients involved in this pilot).

- Regarding the sex of clients included in the analysis, 71.4% (N=30) were female, 21.4% (N=10) were male, 1 client reported their sex as Transgender, and 1 client did not disclose their sex.
- Regarding the age of clients included in the analysis, 54.8% (N=23) were aged 18-34 and 45.2% (N=19) were aged 35+.

In this section of the report, we present the results of the following data analysis:

- A health profile of clients at the start of their involvement with *Survive*.
- A victimisation profile of clients, outlining the nature of the sexual violence experienced by clients.
- Analysis of the changes in IES-R scores, comparing scores before and after involvement with *Survive*. We present this analysis for the sample as a whole, presented by sex, and by age.
- Client reports of accessing the NHS mental health services before and after engagement with *Survive*.
- Client feedback on their experiences of the support received by *Survive*.

Victimisation Experience

As part of the NHS pilot, *Survive* recorded experiences of the nature of the sexual violence experienced and that were shared by clients. Sometimes this information is shared during the referral process, and sometimes clients share further details about their experiences during counselling.

The majority of clients in the NHS pilot had experienced CSA. Almost a quarter of clients had experienced sexual violence in adulthood, and 8.62% of clients had experienced CSA AND sexual violence in adulthood.

Specifically:

- 67.4% (N=39) had experienced CSA.
- 22.41% (N=13) had experienced sexual violence.
- 8.62% (N=5) had experienced CSA and sexual violence.
- 6.90% (N=4) had experienced domestic violence.

Health Impact

As part of the NHS pilot, *Survive* asked clients about their general health during their initial assessment. We have summarised the health issues reported by clients during this assessment. Please note that these are self-report data and not formal diagnoses. However, over half of clients reported 1) suicidal thoughts, behaviours, and/ or attempts, and 2) feelings of anxiety. Furthermore, almost half of the clients reported substance misuse, and almost half reported symptoms of trauma.

Suicide & Self-Harm

- 56.9% (N=33) reported suicidal thoughts, behaviours, and/or attempts.
- 34.48% (N=20) reported self-harm behaviours.

Mental Health

- 55.17% (N=32) reported suffering from anxiety.
- 50% (N=29) suffered from depression.
- 6.9% (N=4) suffered from OCD.
- 1.72% (N=1) reported disordered eating.

Substance Use

- 48.28% (N=28) reported substance misuse.

Trauma Symptoms

- 44.83% (N=26) reported symptoms of trauma.
- 8.62% (N=5) reported insomnia.

Chronic Pain

- 12.07% (N=7) reported chronic pain.

Trauma Symptoms

We examined clients' IES-R scores before and after support from *Survive*. The IES-R scale provides a measure of trauma symptoms and can assess total trauma scores, alongside scores of hypervigilance, avoidance and intrusions.

Does support from *Survive* significantly reduce trauma symptoms in survivors of sexual violence?

Yes, as shown in Figure 1, trauma scores reduced after support from *Survive*. This reduction in trauma symptoms was statistically significant; $t(41)=9.55, p<.001, d=13.83$.

Is the support provided by *Survive* effective for both female and male survivors?

Yes, trauma scores reduced significantly for both female ($t(29)=8.56, p<.001, d=13.43$) and male ($t(9)=3.63, p=.003, d=15.26$) survivors, see Figure 2. The degree of change (as indicated by the d value) was similar for female and male survivors.

Is the support provided by *Survive* effective for both younger and older survivors?

Yes, trauma scores reduced significantly for both younger ($t(22)=7.21, p<.001, d=15.38$) and older ($t(18)=6.64, p<.001, d=11.20$) survivors, see Figure 3. The degree of change (as indicated by the d value) was similar for younger and older survivors.

Figure 1:
Change in IES-R Scores.

Figure 2
Change in IES-R Scores, by sex

Figure 3:
Change in IES-R Scores, by age

Figure 4:
Client (N=57) coping skills following support from *Survive*

Client Feedback

Clients were also provided with the opportunity to self-report on how they felt their coping skills had changed following support. As shown in Figure 4, the majority of clients reported feeling better able to manage their mental health and care for themselves.

Regarding specific coping skills, over three-quarters of clients reported feeling better able to cope with everyday life, and 70% (N=40) of clients reported being able to cope better with their feelings and emotions. As some of the clients in this project stated:

"[Survive] Has helped me become more aware of how I can support myself by using the strategies we have talked about."

"I feel more aware of how my life has impacted on my conditions. Have a greater awareness of how to support myself and be kinder."

Use of NHS Mental Health Services

Part of the evaluation of the NHS pilot focused on examining how accessing support affected clients' use of NHS mental health services. As highlighted in Figures 5 and 6, 33.3% (N=19) of clients reported being on an NHS waiting list for mental health services, and 26.3% (N=15) reported accessing NHS mental health services before accessing support from *Survive*.

Clients were also asked about their use of NHS mental health services following support from *Survive*. As shown in Figure 7, the majority of clients (82.46%, N=47) reported that their use of such services had either *stopped* or *reduced*.

Figure 5: On an NHS waiting list for Mental Health Services before Survive

Figure 6: Accessed NHS Mental Health Services 12 months before accessing Survive

Figure 7: Use of NHS Mental Health Services after accessing support from Survive

SECTION 6

Results: Impact of *Survive*

This section of the report presents the results of our analysis testing the impact of *Survive*'s support on clients' psychological distress and clients' trauma symptoms.

Data Analysis

Survive provided anonymised data from 401 Clients gathered in 2023/24 and 2024/25. Not all clients completed all scales; completion of scales was dependent on the client's needs. Below, we outline the number of participants included in each type of data analysis.

Changes in Psychological Distress

To assess changes in psychological distress, we matched CORE-10 data over time for 261 (65%) clients. Of these clients:

- 67.4% (N=176) were female, and 8% (N=21) were men, 2 clients (0.8%) reported being transgender, and 2 (0.8%) reported being non-binary.
- 75.1% (N=196) were aged 18-44, and 24.9% (N=65) were aged 45+.

Changes in Trauma Symptoms

- To assess changes in trauma scores, we matched IES-R data over time for 139 clients (34.7%). Of these clients:
- 79.9% (N=111) were female, and 9.4% (N=13) were men, 2 clients (1.4%) reported being transgender, and 2 (1.4%) reported being non-binary.
- 74.1% (N=103) were aged 18-44, and 25.9% (N=36) were aged 45+.

Data Analysis

Scores on these scales are presented for clients at the start of their involvement with *Survive* (Time 1) and after completing their therapy with *Survive* (Time 2). Changes in scores are presented for the sample as a whole and:

- by gender (to assess whether support from *Survive* is effective for men and women)
- by age (to assess whether support from *Survive* is effective for younger and older clients)

Psychological Distress

We examined clients' psychological distress and Core 10 scores before and after support from Survive.

Does support from *Survive* significantly reduce psychological distress in survivors of sexual violence?

Yes, Core 10 scores decreased following support from *Survive*, as shown in Figure 8. Our analysis found that psychological distress reduced significantly following involvement with *Survive*; $t(260)=16.65, p<.001, d=7.91$.

Is the support provided by *Survive* effective for both female and male survivors?

Yes, our analysis found that psychological distress was reduced for both female ($t(175)=12.48, p<.001, d=7.78$) and male survivors ($t(20)=4.92, p<.001, d=8.10$). The effect sizes (d values) were similar, suggesting that support from *Survive* reduced psychological distress for both female and male survivors, see Figure 9.

Is the support provided by *Survive* effective for both younger and older survivors?

Yes, our analysis found that psychological distress reduced significantly for both younger ($t(195)=14.21, p<.001, d=7.17$) and older ($t(64)=9.27, p<.001, d=9.38$) survivors, see Figure 10. The effect size for the reduction among older survivors was slightly larger than among young survivors, suggesting a larger reduction in distress scores. However, psychological distress was significantly reduced for both groups.

Figure 8: Change in CORE-10 Scores.

Figure 9: Change in CORE-10 Scores, by sex

Figure 10: Change in CORE-10 Scores, by age

Figure 11: Change in the percentage of clients in the clinically relevant distress score group after accessing support from *Survive*.

Psychological Distress

We also analysed the psychological distress data to consider how engagement with *Survive* reduced distress scores. When scoring the CORE-10, clients' scores can be categorised as healthy, low-level distress, mild distress, moderate distress, moderate to severe distress, and severe distress. As shown in Figure 11, at the start of engagement with *Survive* (Time 1), the majority of clients (60.2%, N=157) reported scores indicating moderate to severe or severe distress. Following engagement with *Survive* (Time 2), this was reduced to 19.1% (N=50) of survivors. Regarding healthy or low-level distress, few clients (8%, N=21) at Time 1 (at the start of engagement with *Survive*) reported scores in these categories. This increased to 46% following engagement with *Survive* (at Time 2).

This analysis suggests a substantial decrease in moderate to severe and severe psychological distress, and an increase in healthy and low-level distress scores in survivors following engagement with *Survive*.

Trauma Symptoms

We examined clients' trauma scores (their IES-R scores) before and after support from *Survive*.

Does support from *Survive* significantly reduce trauma symptoms in survivors of sexual violence?

Yes, as shown in Figure 12, trauma scores reduced after support from *Survive*. This reduction in trauma symptoms was statistically significant; $t(138)=12.36, p<.001, d=20.71$, see Figure 12.

Is the support provided by *Survive* effective for both female and male survivors?

Yes, trauma scores reduced significantly for both female ($t(110)=10.52, p<.001, d=20.70$) and male ($t(12)=4.83, p<.001, d=20.28$) survivors, see Figure 13. The degree of change (as indicated by the d value) was similar for female and male survivors.

Is the support provided by *Survive* effective for both younger and older survivors?

Yes, trauma scores reduced significantly for both younger ($t(102)=12.16, p<.001, d=21.11$) and older ($t(35)=4.22, p<.001, d=21.15$) survivors, see Figure 14. The degree of change (as indicated by the d value) was similar for younger and older survivors.

Figure 12:
Change in IES-R Scores.

Figure 13:
Change in IES-R Scores, by sex

Figure 14:
Change in IES-R Scores, by age

	Total Sample		Females		Males		Younger survivors		Older Survivors	
	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post
Avoidance	1.48 (.96)	0.72 (.83)	1.44 (.93)	.77 (.83)	1.62 (1.19)	.54 (.66)	1.56 (.99)	.74 (.82)	1.25 (.84)	.66 (.86)
Hyperarousal	2.04 (.92)	1.16 (.89)	2.01 (.92)	1.22 (.90)	2.00 (0.92)	1.21 (.90)	2.02 (.95)	1.08 (.83)	2.11 (.97)	1.38 (1.02)
Intrusions	1.90 (.98)	1.00 (.92)	1.88 (1.00)	1.06 (.97)	1.95 (1.10)	.84 (.50)	1.86 (.96)	.90 (.86)	1.98 (1.05)	1.28 (1.07)

Table 1: Changes in IES-R domain scores, after accessing support from *Survive*. presented for the whole sample, by sex and by age

Trauma Symptoms

The IES-R scale also provides scores of trauma symptoms, specifically avoidance, hyperarousal and intrusions. Changes in the mean scores of these symptoms are shown in Table 1. Our analysis found that for the total sample, significant reductions were found for avoidance symptoms: $t(148)=9.89, p<.001, d=.97$, hyperarousal: $t(148)=11.13, p<.001, d=.95$, and intrusions: $t(148)=11.20, p<.001, d=.95$. This reduction in all symptoms was found for both female and male survivors and for younger and older survivors, see below. This analysis suggests a substantial decrease in moderate to severe and severe psychological distress, and an increase in healthy and low-level distress scores in all survivors following engagement with *Survive*.

Females

- Avoidance $t(117)=7.94, p<.001, d=.92$
- Hyperarousal $t(117)=9.81, p<.001, d=.86$
- Intrusions $t(117)=9.61, p<.001, d=.91$

Males

- Avoidance $t(13)=4.163, p<.001, d=1.03$
- Hyperarousal $t(13)=3.36, p=.003, d=1.07$
- Intrusions $t(13)= 3.60, p=.002 d=1.10$

Younger Survivors

- Avoidance $t(117)=7.94, p<.001, d=.92$
- Hyperarousal $t(117)=9.81, p<.001, d=.86$
- Intrusions $t(117)=9.61, p<.001, d=.91$

Older Survivors

- Avoidance $t(13)=4.163, p<.001, d=1.03$
- Hyperarousal $t(13)=3.36, p=.003, d=1.07$
- Intrusions $t(13)= 3.60, p=.002 d=1.10$

Figure 15: Change in percentage of clients in the different categories of IES-R scores, after accessing support from *Survive*.

Trauma Symptoms

We also analysed the trauma data to consider how engagement with *Survive* reduced distress scores. When scoring the IES-R scale, clients' scores can be categorised as being below the threshold for clinical concern, of clinical concern, indicative of a diagnosis of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), and high enough to suppress immune system functioning. As Figure 15 shows, at the start of engagement with *Survive* (Time 1), the majority of clients (88.5%, N=123) reported scores in the high enough to suppress immune system functioning category. Following engagement with *Survive* (Time 2), this was reduced to 42.4% of survivors. Regarding scores below the threshold of clinical concern, few clients (3.6%, N=5) at Time 1 (at the start of engagement with *Survive*) reported scores in this category. This increased following engagement with *Survive* (at Time 2) to 40.3% (N=56).

This analysis suggests a substantial decrease in the proportion of survivors with trauma scores in the high enough to suppress immune system functioning category following engagement with *Survive*.

SECTION 7

Results: Client Voice

In this final results section we report the results of our qualitative data analysis on client feedback on what they thought about their experiences with *Survive*.

Client Feedback

In *Survive's* service evaluation, clients are given the opportunity to share their thoughts about the impact *Survive* has had on them. The key themes identified from these evaluation data are summarised below and explained further on the following pages.

Clients feel acknowledged, listened to and respected, and less isolated. They felt seen as an individual.

Helped clients address related mental health concerns and reflect on their behaviours and feelings.

Helped clients develop and maintain healthy productive relationships.

Clients are able to visualise a happier, healthier future.

Provided clients with strategies and methods of dealing with the consequences of the trauma of experiencing sexual violence.

Assisted with referrals to, engagement with, other support services, which could be difficult to navigate especially when also dealing with trauma and its effects.

Client Feedback

Survive made clients feel less isolated, acknowledged, listened to and respected. They felt seen as an individual.

"After decades of feeling isolated and searching for help, I finally feel that my experience of abuse has been acknowledged".

"I was allowed to bring my dog with me and was made to feel supported and comfortable."

"For the first time in my life I really felt understood and respected during counselling. My counsellor did not try to push me in any direction I did not want to go. Instead, they accepted and respected my own ideas and boundaries".

Survive helped clients address related mental health concerns and reflect on their behaviours and feelings.

"The effect of my usual triggers is massively diminished".

"My experience with the Survive sessions made a great deal of difference to my perspective on my current position, choices, agency, capacity for change, ability to see and work with my emotions, to bring in a compassionate voice and a desire to change the narrative. I've been working on my boundaries both with others and self. I feel I now have a more realistic view of where I am and the struggles I currently face, and a better insight into where I have the potential to grow. I feel infinitely more hopeful, and have higher self-esteem".

"This is life transforming work that brings hope and ability to stay alive".

Survive helped clients develop and maintain healthy, productive relationships.

"Helped me in understanding myself better and to actively engage in a trusting new relationship and with my friends".

"Some previously tricky relationships have vastly improved".

"She really listened to me and what was causing me the most trauma. She gave me coping skills and talked through lots of things with me. I really feel she has helped me the most and in turn this has helped me deal better with my children and their trauma. I feel I am now able to support my children better as she helped me understand how they are feeling and why I get some of the behaviour".

Client Feedback

Survive provided clients with strategies and methods of dealing with the consequences of the trauma of experiencing sexual violence.

"My support worker helped me create a toolbox of coping mechanisms and strategies for when I need them".

"She helped me learn new coping strategies and introduced me to a new spiritual side of me".

Survive assisted with referrals to, engagement with, and other support services, which could be difficult to navigate, especially when also dealing with trauma and its effects.

"I really appreciated their suggestion to join Kyra. This has helped me build my social network".

"The counselling I had received from Survive helped me to be in a position to report the crime, ultimately it went to court and the perpetrator was found guilty and sentenced".

Clients are able to visualise a happier, healthier future.

"For the first time in my life I feel a sense of optimism regarding my ability to get to a place of grounded, stable and compassionate thinking regarding my experiences".

"Given me a whole new look on life and a very positive mind-set for now and the future".

"I feel at peace knowing that my experience won't follow me around like a dark cloud for the rest of my life. It can and will be manageable and I will be able to live a happy and calm life".

"I feel better, and more hopeful for the future".

Client Feedback

Survivors also shared their thoughts on **areas of improvement** at *Survive*. There were two main criticisms, which were not really aimed at *Survive* but reflect the challenges survivors face in accessing appropriate support.

The waiting list was too long, which meant that clients had to wait considerable periods to receive counselling.

"Shorter waiting list because I didn't benefit as much as I could have done had the counselling been provided at the time I was still suffering effects of trauma. I was assessed in August and started 5 months later but I needed it within 3 months ideally because after that I had self-healed mostly".

Most participants were fairly stoic about the waiting list and recognised that often the reasons behind it were outside the control of *Survive*.

"It would be nice to have entered the service earlier as waiting lists are huge. I do understand the strain on voluntary services".

"A shorter waiting time between referral and the counselling starting would have been great, but I appreciate this is very difficult to achieve".

Some clients would have liked longer counselling programmes ie longer than the standard 10 weeks.

"The only thing I don't understand is why after so much trauma we only get 10 weeks, this I don't understand, but the weeks I had were invaluable".

"Part of me would wish for the sessions to run on longer as I felt that I had a great connection with my counsellor and I felt there was more for us to work on".

"I am/was truly grateful for the 10 Sessions I received. Yet unfortunately it did not scratch the surface of a lifetime of sexual, physical, emotional, domestic abuse".

Client Feedback

There was a third area for improvement that several participants mentioned which was probably linked to the first two comments. Some participants felt that at the early stages, when they were waiting for , something could be done to manage the expectations and anxieties of new clients. Such suggestions included:

Greater contact

Some clients reported that whilst on the waiting list, it would have been helpful to receive more information, for example, by keeping the individual informed and providing an estimate of how much longer they may have to wait. This could be done by regular email, pointing out other services *Survive* provides and highlighting that the individual has not “*been forgotten about*”. Other one off suggestions: Inclusion of a ‘legal advocacy scheme’, information in an ‘easy read’ format, and a waiting area to sit before and after appointments.

More detail at the start of the process

Some clients reported that a more in-depth introduction to the process would have been helpful before starting. This could include what would be involved and how the sessions would be run. This information should be available not only to clients but also to those who refer individuals to the service, i.e., GPs. Initial information needed to be constantly reviewed, and any changes communicated quickly and sensitively to avoid losing a client’s “trust”. As one client stated:

“Being clear about the service being provided: During my GP appointment I was told I was being referred for trauma therapy that would likely lead to EMDR, however through reviewing this form, I think I only received 10 weeks of counselling since that was the only 10-week option. There was also no mention of EMDR, either now or in future, even though the doctor has said she believed it would be beneficial so I was just quite confused and think that things could be more clear”.

Client Feedback

Survivors also shared their thoughts on the strengths of Survive. All participants, except one, were highly complimentary about their therapist, highlighting both their professional and personal qualities. They were “kind, calm, made me feel safe, patient and friendly, compassionate, approachable, perceptive, empathic, caring, empowering and gentle”. Clients also highlighted specific areas of strength.

Dedicated Sexual Violence Support

Having access to a service that is dedicated to sexual violence survivors (rather than a generic service) is important to the participants because it means that they can freely talk about anything (i.e., the sexual violence) without worrying about what the counsellor might think or having to protect the counsellor's feelings. This creates a 'safe environment'.

“It has been extremely helpful to speak to a counsellor that I know I can bring anything up with, the sexual abuse specifically, knowing it is a safe environment to do so”.

Also, clients highlighted how *Survive's* dedicated sexual violence counsellors have had specific training and are better able to manage the many issues associated with sexual violence trauma.

“I have to say it is a valuable service and it's there for people who have deep issues that a lot of other services haven't a clue about nor will ever”.

“I have undertaken several courses in CBT and CAT, and although I understand the principles, they are too generalised and unbelievable from the point of view of the challenges I have faced. This has left me untrusting of the mental health services in this area. Survive is the complete opposite, their help has been invaluable and have helped me explore the most distressing episodes of my life”.

SECTION 8

Discussion

In this section we highlight the key findings from our analysis.

Discussion

Experiencing CSA, rape and/or sexual assault can have a profound impact on mental health. Evidence suggests that encouraging survivors to seek help and trauma-informed counselling has the potential to reduce the psychological impact of such experiences. The aim of our report was to examine the impact support from *Survive* can have on survivors of CSA, rape and sexual assault.

Survivors present with a range of health issues

Our analysis found that survivors face a range of health issues. Our analysis of *Survive*'s NHS pilot data shows the complex range of health, mental health, and substance misuse issues faced by survivors. Such findings support previous research, which has highlighted the health impact of sexual trauma¹²⁻¹⁶.

Feedback from clients suggests that after accessing support from *Survive*, their use of NHS mental health services either reduced or stopped.

***Survive* significantly reduces symptoms of psychological distress and trauma.**

Psychological distress in survivors was significantly reduced following support from *Survive*. This reduction was found for all genders and ages. Support from *Survive* also led to a significant reduction in trauma symptoms. This was found for all forms of trauma measures (intrusion, hyperarousal, avoidance) and was found for all genders and age groups. These findings highlight the impact of support from *Survive* on psychological wellbeing and support previous research highlighting the benefit of trauma-informed approaches for survivors of CSA, rape and sexual assault.

Discussion

Positive praise from clients

The feedback from survivors highlighted how the counsellors at *Survive* made them feel safe, trusted and understood. Survivors highlighted how important it is to have a sexual violence-specific service, where sexual violence can be discussed openly without judgment. Such support was valued highly compared with more generalised mental health services.

Evaluation of this study

We report for the first time on how a trauma-informed counselling service for survivors of CSA, rape and sexual assault reduces use of NHS mental health services. The NHS pilot, however, was based on a small sample of clients and relied on self-reports of clients' use of NHS mental health services. Our initial findings would benefit from further longitudinal study. Our secondary data analysis benefitted from a large sample of clients, including male and female survivors of varied ages. This enabled us to test the impact of *Survive* on a range of clients. Further, data on psychological distress and trauma symptoms were collected using well-validated scales (the CORE-10 and IES-R). These strengths reflect the high quality of data gathered by *Survive*, which enabled this data analysis. However, we assessed symptom change only at two time points: before and after accessing support from *Survive*. Further investigation of the benefit of *Survive* would benefit from a longitudinal study to examine whether the positive impact reported in our analyses persists over the longer term. Finally, this evaluation focused on one aspect of *Survive*'s work; future studies could also examine the efficacy of *Survive*'s 20-week trauma therapy programme and their support work.

CONCLUSION

The Impact of *Survive*

The findings of our report highlight the profound and wide-ranging negative health impact of experiencing CSA, rape and sexual assault. Yet our findings also show how support from *Survive*, as an example of trauma-informed counselling, reduced symptoms of psychological distress and trauma in survivors of CSA, rape and sexual assault, and reduced use of NHS services. Previous research has highlighted how experiences of such forms of sexual violence can have a negative and lifelong impact on those harmed. Yet the findings of our evaluation clearly highlight how support from *Survive* has helped survivors to cope with their experiences, adapt and move forward. While support can never erase such traumatic experiences, the support provided by *Survive* has clearly supported survivors to live healthier and happier lives.

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About Survive – Support for survivors of rape and sexual abuse

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